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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Bimanual Motion Primitives for Manipulating 3D Deformable Objects Having Biological Tissues on a Planar Surface With Passive End-Effectors

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ABSTRACT Manipulating deformable objects (DOs) that change shape during operations poses a challenge for robots due to the complexity of modelling and predicting the object's state. This challenge is critical for the food industry, where collaborative robots will assist workers in processing and packaging food products. Most meat products are three-dimensional DOs (3D-DOs) composed of biological tissues, which give them viscoelastic and anisotropic properties that make their behaviour highly unpredictable and challenging to model. To address this challenge and minimise food cross-contamination, dual-arm robots and non-actuated end-effectors, such as chopsticks, are used to provide more flexibility, especially when working with objects in confined spaces, and reduce tool actuation time. Our goal is to develop a methodology for manipulating predominant convex 3D-DOs composed of biological tissues on a planar surface, altering their position and orientation while minimising their deformations. To accomplish this, we propose bimanual motion primitives utilising a novel geometric approach. Effectiveness is measured by the Intersection-over-Union ratio and object centroid error metrics through 180 chicken-breast, 36 pork-loin-steak experiments, and 96 comparative experiments with heuristic methods for rigid objects.

INDEX TERMS Bimanual manipulation, motion and path planning, deformable object.

I. INTRODUCTION

The food industry plays a critical role in population growth, but it remains a labour-intensive sector with only a 24% rate of job automation in the food service industry [1], resulting in inconsistent product quality and low productivity. Integrating robotics in food production is essential but poses challenges in handling materials, requiring specialised equipment and expertise [2].

One common task in food industrial manufacturing is batching and packaging soft, deformable, and tacky products such as meats [3]. The task requires a pick-and-place step

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to move products from a conveyor to a food container (e.g., a Gastronorm container), which is commonly handled by delta robots with exceptional speed and accuracy. However, their lack of flexibility results in placed meat products requiring a refinement step to look appealing to consumers, as shown in Figure 1. This refinement step involves minor adjustments to the objects within a confined space by pushing from the sides rather than pinching and grasping the objects. Therefore, traditional grippers may not be, but chopstick-type End-effectors (EEs) are suitable for the motion primitives of these adjustments and also hygiene concerns [4]. Chopsticks are a simple yet familiar tool that humans are proficient in using. They have great versatility, reachability, and precision and have inspired the development of robots

FIGURE 1. The sorting input and expectation of a box of chicken breasts from a food production line.

capable of performing complex manipulation skills through learning [5], [6].

In the main literature, most food products can be described as Deformable Objects (DOs). However, studies on DOs are less extensive than those on Rigid Objects due to the higher complexity involved in modelling, perception, and control [7], [8], and even less for three-dimensional DOs (3D-DOs). Most existing studies on 3D-DOs have focused on deformation measurements to learn specific object behaviours and shape them as desired [9], [10], [11], [12], [13]. Furthermore, some focused on cutting/splitting food [14], [15], [16], or picking up tasks [5], [6], [17]. None of these studies has focused explicitly on meat products, as the objects examined typically display only *visco-elastic* or *anisotropic* behaviour. As a result, meat products, having both of these characteristics, continue to pose challenges for robotic handling in industrial production.

Focusing on the refinement step in food packaging, our goal is to develop bimanual motion primitives to alter the position and orientation of a 3D-DO having biological tissues with minimal deformations within a plane using chopsticks. The approach is heuristic, utilising only geometric data and necessitating assumptions regarding shape and density. This study could lay the groundwork for more advanced manipulations, even with limited knowledge of object materials. It could potentially serve as a dependable framework for learning-based approaches, showcasing the practical applications of our research.

The remainder of this article is organised as follows: In Section II, we will provide a brief overview of recent studies on DOs in Robotics with a focus on modelling, perception, and manipulation. Section III will outline our proposed approach, which involves generating trajectories for Manipulating Points (MPs) using only geometric data. Section IV describes the experiment setup and results, followed by Section V, which presents the concluding remarks.

II. RELATED WORKS

Material parameters are an important component in understanding and predicting the deformation of objects against

external impacts. This component was referred to as *strain* ϵ and commonly assumed to have a linear relation with the external stress [7], [8]. Depending on the response of the object once the impacts are removed, the deformation can be classified as *plastic*, *elastic*, and *elasto-plastic*. Objects can be permanently deformed (*plastic*, like papers), or return to their original shape (*elastic*, like rubber bands), or exhibit behaviour between original and deformed shapes (*elasto-plastic*). The term *visco-elastic* [18] describes an object that behaves like a fluid and a solid material while exhibiting a time-dependent strain, often seen in meat products. Consequently, *visco-elastic* deformation complicates the automation of handling meat products due to varying time-dependent strain among similar objects.

Handling DOs requires different techniques and approaches in Object Modelling, Perception, and Manipulation. [19] highlights the vast diversity of methodologies used across shape modelling, dynamic simulation, learning, and control in DOM. It reveals the complex interconnections and methodological variability across perception, modelling, and control, underscoring the challenge of integrating these components in a unified framework.

Modelling methods can be categorised into the geometric approach and physics-based approaches. In both approaches, the object is represented by a network of nodes, such as a mesh for quantitative models or a template for qualitative models [8]. The geometric approach focuses on the spatial relationships between model vertices, while the physics-based approach extensively utilises the material parameters to predict the object's dynamic behaviour. Well-known approaches in the physics-based approach are Mass-spring-damper systems, Position-based dynamics, and Continuum mechanics [8]. They are the foundation for simulation engines, e.g., MuJoCo [20] and NVIDIA Physx [21]. However, estimating material parameters can be challenging, especially for meat products, as they are time-variant and specific to each specimen. Research on the geometric approach is still expanding to find solutions independent of precise physical modelling. A Jacobian-based method [22] was introduced in 2013, continuously extended and made into a framework that avoids the need for precise modelling or high-fidelity simulation [23].

In perception, machine vision and force sensing are two common techniques used in the main literature. Vision is used in tasks where the object is undergoing large deformation, requiring a vision system to acquire the object contour on the image plane or form a mesh of the object for modelling. Vision systems can be used for instance segmentation, visual servoing, object reconstruction [9], or deformation tracking [24]. Force and tactile sensing, in contrast, can read local deformation on selective parts to estimate the global material parameters. Although the number of studies employing both techniques on 3D-DOs is limited [8], force and tactile sensing can be effectively integrated with vision systems to enhance precision and control.

Manipulation encompasses various challenges, such as identifying MPs and planning joint trajectories for dual-arm position/velocity/force control. Most previous studies on 3D-DOs utilised grippers for grasping and shaping tasks, while chopstick-type EEs were only used to learn deformation estimation. In a recent study [25], a chopstick and fixed circular contact were used on a flat surface for a squeezing task, focusing on identifying MPs for a single-arm robot manipulating a sponge, an isotropic elastic object to prevent contact sliding and separation. In contrast, most meat products are considered as 3D-DOs composed of biological tissues, which exhibit both *anisotropic* and *visco-elastic* characteristics. Manipulation of 3D-DOs has primarily been considered for robotic assistance in surgical applications [27], including teleoperation, high-dexterity tasks, and precise force measurements.

III. APPROACH DESCRIPTION

This study uses the following variable notations: bold capitalised letter for 3D coordinates; bold lower case letter for vectors; lowercase letter for scalar; and calligraphic symbol for sets, such as \mathcal{C} with its cardinality is $|\mathcal{C}|$.

Let us consider a flat surface described as a x, y -plane T_{surface} at the height z_{surface} with respect to the origin of the robot. A 3D-DO specimen lies on the plane T_{surface} . The goal is to change the object's pose on the surface, minimising the 3D-DO permanent deformations. To accomplish this without having force/tactile sensors, we propose a solution to identify the object's MPs and formulate primitives; thereby, any robot system with machine vision can also use this implementation to achieve the same goal. The scenario can be seen via our setup in Figure 2

FIGURE 2. The capture of the setup. The yellow area is the surface that the objects are lying on, which is orthogonal to the camera's principal axis.

With the given scenario, we want to introduce the following assumptions.

Assumption 1: The object exhibits predominant convexity, with a high convexity ratio close to 1.

Assumption 2: The object has nearly uniform density. This means the centre of mass of the object can be estimated through a discrete model of itself without knowing any material parameters.

Assumption 3: When applying force to the object lying on the plane T_{surface} with the vertical chopstick described above, the object cannot be flipped. Therefore, any motion primitives with the aforementioned tools to the sides of the object will only deform and/or slide the object.

These assumptions are typical characteristics of meat products, such as chicken breasts and pork loin steaks. They have the characteristics of a 3D-DO and exhibit unknown time-variant elasticity, stickiness, fragility, and friction coefficients. We made observations on the reaction of the object to external stress from the side using vertical chopsticks. In all cases, the object first deforms and then starts sliding. As shown in Figure 3, forces (teal vector) were applied on the edge of the object (green contour) towards the centroid (red dot) to observe different levels of deformation.

FIGURE 3. The deformation tests on the chicken breast using vertical chopsticks.

Figure 3 shows that after a certain deformation toward the object's centroid (which can be acquired through software libraries like OpenCV), the whole object started moving out of its original position, as indicated by moving outside of its captured contour in the vision system. Additionally, the degree of deformation needed to move the object depends on the curvature and thickness of the body part around the contact point. Hence, there must be a *central region* on the object that indicates the point at which the object starts moving after being deformed, and this central region can be estimated using vision techniques. Therefore, the approach of this study is to estimate this *central region* using a stereo-vision system and then plan primitives based on this estimation. As a result, the primitives will involve two motions: deforming (to reach the *central region* and initiate the object movement) and sliding (to change the object's position and orientation). In this study, our focus will be on translation and rotation primitives. Their goal is to alter the object's position and orientation, respectively. Their formulation consists of two phases:

- 1) Model the object and estimate the *central region* of the object that indicates the points at which the object starts to move after being deformed. We propose the term *rigid-like* to refer to this *central region*.
- 2) Find MPs and formulate primitives for a dual-arm robot using the estimation from phase 1 to move the object to a new position or angle.

These phases are visualised in Figure 4. Phase 1, which includes object modelling and estimating *rigid-like* region, will be explained in subsection III-A. Phase 2, focusing on

Motion Primitives, will be described in subsection III-B. The generated trajectories for EEs will be executed using the existing work Extended MoveIt Framework in [28], and the evaluation will be described in Section IV.

FIGURE 4. The UML activity diagram of motion primitives development.

A. IDENTIFICATION OF OBJECT RIGID-LIKE REGION

The first step is to identify the object using edge detection or active contour methods. By filtering the identification with the Point Cloud dataset, a set of 3D points representing the visible surface of the object is obtained and denoted as $\mathcal{P}_{\text{visible}}$. Then the projection of $\mathcal{P}_{\text{visible}}$ on the plane T_{surface} is called $\mathcal{P}_{\text{projection}}$, and the contour wrapping around $\mathcal{P}_{\text{projection}}$ is called $\mathcal{C}_{\text{projection}}$. Because the object is a 3D-DO, we discretize the projection $\mathcal{P}_{\text{visible}} \rightarrow \mathcal{P}_{\text{projection}}$ using a sampling vector $\mathbf{v}_z = [0, 0, d_z]$ where d_z is the sampling period. Each gap between $\mathbf{P}_{i,\text{vis}} \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{vis}}$ and its projection $\mathbf{P}_{i,\text{proj}} \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{projection}}$ is sampled as follows:

$$\mathcal{P}_{\text{sampling},i} = \left\{ \mathbf{P}_{i,\text{proj}} + k\mathbf{v}_z \mid \forall k \in \mathbb{N}, 0 < k < \frac{\|\mathbf{P}_{i,\text{vis}} - \mathbf{P}_{i,\text{proj}}\|}{d_z} \right\} \tag{1}$$

By applying Equation 1 on every projection in $\mathcal{P}_{\text{visible}} \rightarrow \mathcal{P}_{\text{projection}}$, a set representing the discretised object is obtained, denoted as $\mathcal{O} = \bigcup_i \mathcal{P}_{\text{sampling},i} \cup \mathcal{P}_{\text{visible}} \cup \mathcal{P}_{\text{projection}}$.

From Assumption 2, the centroid of the object $\mathbf{P}_{\text{centroid}}$ and its projection on plane T_{surface} , denoted as $\bar{\mathbf{P}}_{\text{centroid}}$, can be estimated as follows:

$$\mathbf{P}_{\text{centroid}} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{O}|} \sum_{\mathbf{o}_i \in \mathcal{O}} \mathbf{o}_i \tag{2}$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{P}}_{\text{centroid}} = [x_{\mathbf{P}_{\text{centroid}}}, y_{\mathbf{P}_{\text{centroid}}}, z_{\text{surface}}] \tag{3}$$

Note: Assumption 1 can guarantee that $\bar{\mathbf{P}}_{\text{centroid}}$ lies inside the polygon made of $\mathcal{C}_{\text{projection}}$.

Next, \mathcal{O} is utilised for the *rigid-like* contour estimation. From Figure 3, a correlation was discovered between the contact point and the degree of deformation prior to movement. The thicker the object’s body around the contact point, the less deformation is required to move the object. This relation is also true for the curvature around the contact point. Arbitrarily, calling the first contact point of the chopstick $\mathbf{C}_{i,\text{proj}} \in \mathcal{C}_{\text{projection}}$ and the start-moving point \mathbf{T}_i on plane T_{surface} correlated to $\mathbf{C}_{i,\text{proj}}$, a ratio α_i is defined as follows:

$$\alpha_i = \frac{\|\mathbf{T}_i - \bar{\mathbf{P}}_{\text{centroid}}\|}{\|\mathbf{C}_{i,\text{proj}} - \bar{\mathbf{P}}_{\text{centroid}}\|} \tag{4}$$

FIGURE 5. A section view of discretised projections (purple) of visible Point Cloud (yellow) toward the surface.

Let \mathcal{A} be the set of α for different points in $\mathcal{C}_{\text{projection}}$ using Equation 4. Then \mathcal{A} can be gathered by either manual conduct on selective points as in Figure 3 or with programmed robot manipulation. According to the previous discussion, α increases when the contact point is in a thick and low-curvature part and decreases in the reverse. Therefore, we propose the term *local density* to measure the resistance around point $\mathbf{C}_{i,\text{proj}}$ on the edge of the object by counting the neighbouring points in \mathcal{O} near $\mathbf{C}_{i,\text{proj}}$ itself. This can be done by having a r -radius cylinder at $\mathbf{C}_{i,\text{proj}}$ and counting points in \mathcal{O} positioned inside the cylinder. To gather a set of $\mathcal{N} \subset \mathbb{N}$, a *local density survey* goes through points in $\mathcal{C}_{\text{projection}}$, as shown in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Local Density Survey

```

 $\mathcal{N} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
for  $\mathbf{P}_i \in \mathcal{C}_{\text{projection}}$  do
   $n \leftarrow 0$ 
  for  $\mathbf{O}_j \in \mathcal{O}$  do
    if  $\|[\mathbf{x}_{\mathbf{P}_i} - \mathbf{x}_{\mathbf{O}_j}, \mathbf{y}_{\mathbf{P}_i} - \mathbf{y}_{\mathbf{O}_j}]^T\| < r$  then
       $n \leftarrow n + 1$ 
    end if
  end for
  Append  $n$  to  $\mathcal{N}$ 
end for
  
```

The next step is to estimate the *rigid-like* region by making a relation between two sets \mathcal{N} and \mathcal{A} . Let $n_{\text{min}}, n_{\text{max}}$ be the minimum and maximum of \mathcal{N} and $\alpha_{\text{min}}, \alpha_{\text{max}}$ be the minimum and maximum of \mathcal{A} . Assuming the relation is linear, then α_i at point $\mathbf{C}_{i,\text{proj}} \in \mathcal{C}_{\text{projection}}$ with local density of n_i from Algorithm 1 can be approximated as:

$$\alpha_i = f_5(n_i) = \frac{\alpha_{\text{max}} - \alpha_{\text{min}}}{n_{\text{max}} - n_{\text{min}}} (n_i - n_{\text{min}}) + \alpha_{\text{min}} \tag{5}$$

The *rigid-like* contour estimation is shown in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 Finding $\mathcal{C}_{\text{rigid}}$

```

 $\mathcal{C}_{\text{rigid}} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
for  $\mathbf{C}_{i,\text{proj}} \in \mathcal{C}_{\text{projection}}$  do
   $\alpha_i \leftarrow f_5(n_i \in \mathcal{S}_n)$ 
  Append  $\alpha_i (\mathbf{C}_{i,\text{proj}} - \bar{\mathbf{P}}_{\text{centroid}}) + \bar{\mathbf{P}}_{\text{centroid}}$  to  $\mathcal{C}_{\text{rigid}}$ 
end for
  
```

The estimation outputs a 3D polygon $\mathcal{C}_{\text{rigid}}$ on plane T_{surface} , which might be noisy due to the discretisation. The iterative respacing of polygonal curves algorithm [29] can be

used to smooth the polygon. As a result of Phase 1, the *rigid-like* contour estimation can be visualised in Figure 6.

FIGURE 6. The visualisation of rigid-like body part estimation. The gradient particles show the thickness of the object, and the yellow circle represents the $\bar{P}_{\text{centroid}}$. The black dot line represents the $C_{\text{projection}}$, and the red dot line represents the C_{rigid} . The blue circles represent the local survey for each point on the contour. The red arrows show the shrinking from $C_{i,\text{proj}} \in C_{\text{projection}}$ to rigid-like contour $C_{i,\text{rigid}} \in C_{\text{rigid}}$.

B. MANIPULATION PRIMITIVES

Phase 2 focuses on finding MPs and motion planning for translating and rotating primitives. The translation primitive targets moving an object to a new position. When sliding an object on a flat surface using two vertical chopsticks, it is best to apply forces perpendicular to the longer dimension of the object for stability, smooth motion, and keeping a greater distance between EEs from collisions. Therefore, this study focuses on bidirectional translation perpendicular to the long axis of the object. For the rotation, the goal is to rotate the object around its centroid by having two opposite EE movements from opposite sides of the object.

Since the object under the external impacts will be deformed before making any movements, there must be two main motions: deforming and sliding. Deforming motions are the travelling path of EE from points on $C_{\text{projection}}$ to correlated points on C_{rigid} , whereas sliding motions are the actual movements making the whole object move. Therefore, the definition of the object's frame is needed to formulate MPs and generate motion primitives. The coordinate frame of the object is defined as follows:

- The origin of the frame is the projection of the 3D centroid $\bar{P}_{\text{centroid}}$ of the object on plane T_{surface} .
- The z-axis of the frame is parallel with the normal vector of the plane T_{surface} .
- The x-axis of the frame is the orientation vector indicating the yaw angle of the object, denoted as \mathbf{v} , which will be used for trajectory planning.

To find MPs for manipulation primitives, the two furthest subcentroids of the $\mathcal{P}_{\text{rigid}}$ can be used for deforming and sliding motion planning. The K-Means Clustering (K-Means) algorithm can be used to cluster $\mathcal{P}_{\text{rigid}}$ into two subsets, with the mean of each subset being a subcentroid. However, the result might differ based on the initial means. Therefore, the Orthogonal Distance Regression (ODR) is used to find the best-fitting line of the set. Having the initial means aligned with the best-fitting line can help the K-Means algorithm output the most distant means possible. Hence, these subcentroids and $\bar{P}_{\text{centroid}}$ can be used to estimate the

long-dimension axis of the object. The projections of these subcentroids, denoted as \bar{C}_1, \bar{C}_2 , and the orientation vector, denoted as \mathbf{v} , are formulated as follows:

- 1) Project $\mathcal{P}_{\text{rigid}}$ to plane T_{surface} to get $\bar{\mathcal{P}}_{\text{rigid}}$.
- 2) Use ODR on $\bar{\mathcal{P}}_{\text{rigid}}$ to find the best fitting line.
- 3) Initialize two points \bar{C}_1, \bar{C}_2 having $\bar{P}_{\text{centroid}}$ as their middle point and the segment $\bar{C}_1\bar{C}_2$ being parallel with the fitting line in Step 2.
- 4) Run K-Means on $\bar{\mathcal{P}}_{\text{rigid}}$ with initial means \bar{C}_1, \bar{C}_2 . The algorithm outputs new \bar{C}_1, \bar{C}_2 with the number of elements assigned to each. These final means are the projection of the subcentroids we want to formulate. Let \bar{C}_1 be the projection of the significant subcentroid (being assigned with more elements in $\bar{\mathcal{P}}_{\text{rigid}}$).
- 5) Formulate the orientation vector as $\mathbf{v} = \bar{C}_1 - \bar{P}_{\text{centroid}}$.

These steps can be seen in the first three drawings in Figure 7.

To alter the object's position by pushing from the same side or the object's orientation by pushing two opposite sides of the object, two MPs in the C_{rigid} are needed for sliding motions for each case. Therefore, four possible MPs are needed for all possible cases. Hence, four MPs on the $C_{\text{projection}}$ are also required for deforming motions. MPs are formulated based on \bar{C}_1, \bar{C}_2 and the orientation vector \mathbf{v} . The formulation is as follows:

- 1) On plane T_{surface} , project \bar{C}_1, \bar{C}_2 perpendicularly with \mathbf{v} onto C_{rigid} to get a set of 04 MPs on *rigid-like* contour, denoted as $\mathcal{M}_{\text{rigid}}$.
- 2) Reorder $\mathcal{M}_{\text{rigid}}$ to comply with quadrant indexing by having \mathbf{v} as the x-axis in plane T_{surface} as a Cartesian coordinate plane.
- 3) Find the intersection of each ray starting from $\bar{P}_{\text{centroid}}$ to each point in $\mathcal{M}_{\text{rigid}}$ with $C_{\text{projection}}$ to get a set of 04 MPs for deforming motions, denoted as $\mathcal{M}_{\text{projection}}$.

Let $\angle(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b})$ be the angle between \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} within the range of $[-\pi, \pi)$. Then, formulated MPs satisfy these properties:

- If $M_{j,\text{rigid}} \in \mathcal{M}_{\text{rigid}}$ is the perpendicular projection of $\bar{C}_i \in \{\bar{C}_1, \bar{C}_2\}$ with \mathbf{v} , then $\sin\angle(\mathbf{v}, \bar{C}_i - M_{j,\text{rigid}}) = \pm 1$.
- In addition, if $M_{k,\text{proj}} \in \mathcal{M}_{\text{projection}}$ satisfies $\bar{P}_{\text{centroid}}, M_{j,\text{rigid}}$, and $M_{k,\text{proj}}$ being collinear, then $\cos\angle(M_{k,\text{proj}} - M_{j,\text{rigid}}, M_{j,\text{rigid}} - \bar{P}_{\text{centroid}}) = 1$.

Since the dataset is discrete, we want to calculate the sine and cosine values of every element in C_{rigid} and $C_{\text{projection}}$. Then, argmax , argmin , and argsort functions are used to find the peak value indexes. The details and visualisation of the MPs formulation are shown in Algorithm 3 and Figure 7.

Next, an estimated frame of the object at the new state is needed. Calling the directional translating distance d and rotating angle φ , the estimation of points in the object at the new state is the transformation of points in the original ones. Denoting the estimation of arbitrary point \mathbf{P} from the original object at the new state as \mathbf{P}^{est} , the transformation for translation and rotation can be described as shown in

FIGURE 7. The illustration of subcentroids, orientation vector, and MPs formulation. The orange arrow from the red circle toward the significant subcentroid is the orientation vector.

Algorithm 3 Finding MPs $\mathcal{M}_{\text{rigid}}$ and $\mathcal{M}_{\text{projection}}$

```

 $S_\theta \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
 $\mathcal{M}_{\text{rigid}} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
 $\mathcal{M}_{\text{projection}} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
for  $\bar{C}_i \in \{\bar{C}_1, \bar{C}_2\}$  do
     $S_{\text{sin}} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
    for  $C_{j,\text{rigid}} \in \mathcal{C}_{\text{rigid}}$  do
        Append  $\sin \angle (C_{j,\text{rigid}} - \bar{C}_i, \mathbf{v})$  to  $S_{\text{sin}}$ 
    end for
     $j_{\text{max}} \leftarrow \text{argmax}(S_{\text{sin}})$ 
     $j_{\text{min}} \leftarrow \text{argmin}(S_{\text{sin}})$ 
    Append  $C_{j_{\text{max}},\text{rigid}}, C_{j_{\text{min}},\text{rigid}} \in \mathcal{C}_{\text{rigid}}$  to  $\mathcal{M}_{\text{rigid}}$ 
end for
for  $M_{i,\text{rigid}} \in \mathcal{M}_{\text{rigid}}$  do
    Append  $\angle (M_{i,\text{rigid}} - \bar{P}_{\text{centroid}}, \mathbf{v})$  to  $S_\theta$ 
end for
 $i_3, i_4, i_1, i_2 \leftarrow \text{argsort}(S_\theta)$ 
 $\mathcal{M}_{\text{rigid}} \leftarrow \{M_{i_1,\text{rigid}}, M_{i_2,\text{rigid}}, M_{i_3,\text{rigid}}, M_{i_4,\text{rigid}}\}$ 
for  $M_{i,\text{rigid}} \in \mathcal{M}_{\text{rigid}}$  do
     $S_{\text{cos}} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
    for  $C_{j,\text{proj}} \in \mathcal{C}_{\text{projection}}$  do
        Append  $\cos \angle (C_{j,\text{proj}} - M_{i,\text{rigid}}, M_{i,\text{rigid}} - \bar{P}_{\text{centroid}})$  to  $S_{\text{cos}}$ 
    end for
     $j_{\text{max}} \leftarrow \text{argmax}(S_{\text{cos}})$ 
    Append  $C_{j_{\text{max}},\text{proj}} \in \mathcal{C}_{\text{projection}}$  to  $\mathcal{M}_{\text{projection}}$ 
end for

```

Equations 6 & 7 are used estimate the new positions of $\mathcal{C}_{\text{projection}}$, $\mathcal{C}_{\text{rigid}}$, and $\mathcal{M}_{\text{rigid}}$ by the end of the manipulation, denoted as $\mathcal{C}_{\text{projection}}^{\text{est}}$, $\mathcal{C}_{\text{rigid}}^{\text{est}}$, and $\mathcal{M}_{\text{rigid}}^{\text{est}}$. Then, deforming and sliding motions are formulated based on $\mathcal{M}_{\text{projection}}$, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{rigid}}$, and $\mathcal{M}_{\text{rigid}}^{\text{est}}$ as shown in Figure 8. In addition, the starting point of deforming motion can be set further away from $M_{i,\text{proj}} \in \mathcal{M}_{\text{projection}}$.

FIGURE 8. The planning of translation and rotation primitives.

Equations 6 & 7, respectively.

$$P^{\text{est}} = (P - P_{\text{centroid}}) + P_{\text{centroid}}^{\text{est}}$$

where $\begin{cases} \sin \angle (P_{\text{centroid}}^{\text{est}} - P_{\text{centroid}}, \mathbf{v}) = \text{sgn}(d) \\ \|P_{\text{centroid}}^{\text{est}} - P_{\text{centroid}}\| = d \end{cases}$ (6)

$$P^{\text{est}} = f_7(P, \varphi)$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\varphi) & -\sin(\varphi) & 0 \\ \sin(\varphi) & \cos(\varphi) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} (P - P_{\text{centroid}}) + P_{\text{centroid}}$$

(7)

For rotation primitive, quadrant indexes are used to select rigid-like MPs used in sliding motions. Having tool-centre points (TCPs) move like a force couple around the centroid will reduce effort and keep the centroid fixed. Specifically, Points 2 and 4 are chosen for counterclockwise rotation, while Points 1 and 3 are for the reverse direction. In addition, instead of having sliding motions between original and estimated MPs as straight lines, the travelling path can be represented as a series of k_{arc} -polylines in the form of an arc to avoid compressing the object if φ is too large.

The formulation is shown in Equation 8.

$$\mathcal{P}_{arc,i} = \left\{ f_7 \left(\mathbf{M}_{i,rigid}, \frac{m\varphi}{k_{arc}} \right) \mid \forall m \in \mathbb{N}, 0 < m \leq k_{arc} \right\} \quad (8)$$

The illustration of the primitives is shown in Figure 9.

FIGURE 9. The illustration of Translating (left) and Rotating (right) Motions Planning. **Left:** R_1, R_2, D_1, D_2 are used. **Right:** The grey sketch represents the $C_{rigid}^{est}, C_{projection}^{est}, R_2, R_4, D_2, D_4$ are used for counterclockwise rotation.

With the literature review as shown in Table 1, we found that there was no study on developing a heuristic approach for moving and rearranging meat products within a plane using dual-arm robots equipped with non-actuated end-effectors. Therefore, this research aims to develop bimanual motion primitives based on vision that can change the position and orientation of a 3D-DO with minimal deformations within a plane using chopsticks. For this study, chicken breasts and pork loin steak were used for testing as they are common meat products in packaging and sorting tasks in food industrial production lines. Our work is novel compared to existing studies due to the unique characteristics of the object and the manipulation scenarios we are addressing.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

The experimental setup is shown in Figure 2. The camera is an Intel RealSense Camera D455, which provides colour and depth frames for PointCloud generation. Testing objects are put on a black tray to ease object recognition. A Vision Application is developed in ROS to handle vision processing, user input, and planning.

Two different types of experiments were conducted. First, we tested the validity of our proposed method with various meat products, specifically chicken breasts and pork loin. Second, we compared the performance of our approach with other planar manipulation heuristics. Due to limited research on planar pushing for deformable objects, we adapted planar pushing methods from rigid object studies: *single-point* and *line-contact* pushing. Unlike the proposed method (I), the object’s orientation and baseline are formulated using the centroid and primary subcentroid. Then, for *line-contact* pushing, MPs are the projections of either the object’s subcentroids (II) or the vertices that trisect the baseline (III). *Single-point* pushing defines MPs based on projections of the object’s centroid and subcentroids (IV).

Six chicken breasts and six pork loin steaks were used for experimental validation, and six other chicken breasts were used to compare the heuristic approaches. All objects were tested within one hour after being unboxed with a room temperature of 26 – 27°C. For experimental parameters, we used $d_z = 2\text{mm}$ as the discrete step in Figure 5, $r = 5\text{mm}$ in Algorithm 1, and the TCP maximum speed of 100mm/s. α in *rigid-like* contour estimation was set within a range of [0.6, 0.95] for chicken breasts and [0.8, 0.95] for pork loin steaks.

The evaluation metrics, IoU ratio, centroid error, and orientation deviation, measure the precision of the manipulation. For IoU ratio, the areas of $C_{projection}$ and $C_{desired}$ are taken into account, which only loses accuracy due to distortion and noise in the Point Cloud data generation of the Camera. For centroid error, the centroid is based on the Point Cloud dataset, so the accuracy is on the same level as the IoU ratio. The metric of orientation deviation relies on the object’s frame formulation and modelling precision, which is heavily impacted by multiple data discretisations. Therefore, orientation deviation is used as an advisable metric only.

FIGURE 10. The results of 90 translation and 90 rotating experiments using the proposed method on chicken breasts.

Table 2 summarises experiments conducted on chicken breasts and pork loin steaks, proving the validity of the approach with different meat products. Focusing on chicken breasts, Figure 10 shows that our approach (I) is highly precise with short-range primitives and gradually loses accuracy at greater ranges. The centroid error metric indicates that translating experiments have higher errors and a wider spread of trends compared to rotating ones. The orientation deviation comes up to 24° with wide spreads on both motion types. It also shows the increasing trend of deviation against the extent of motion range in both primitives.

Figure 11 and Table 2 compare the performance of our solution (I) with the three aforementioned heuristic approaches (II, III, and IV). This comparison shows that the proposed method (I) produces more consistent results with lower errors. In some cases, the single-point pushing (IV) had

TABLE 1. Comparison of the reviewed studies highlighting the gap in the solution for 3D-DOs manipulation. No studies have primarily focused on meat products exhibiting anisotropic and visco-elastic characteristics.

Related Works	Perception	EE types	Manipulation Tasks	Approach
[5], [6]	Vision systems	Actuated	Grasping/Picking	Learning-based
[9]–[13]	Vision systems	Actuated	Shaping	Learning-based
[14]	Proximity sensors & Vision systems	Non-actuated	Cutting	Heuristics
[15]	Force sensors & Vision systems	Non-actuated	Cutting	Heuristics
[16]	Haptic sensors	Actuated	Cutting, Splitting, Flipping, Picking up, Moving	Learning-based
[25]	Vision systems	Non-actuated	Shaping	Heuristics
[26]	Vision systems	Actuated	Roll-Up, Dumpling, Drilling, Pouring	Learning-based

TABLE 2. Summary of Quantitative Experiment Results on chicken breasts (180 experiments) and pork loin steaks (36 experiments) and 96 Comparative Experiment Results using different heuristics. (best results highlighted in bold)
I: Proposed method, II: Object’s Subcentroids, III: Trisecting Object’s Baseline, IV: Single-point Pushing.

Evaluation Metrics		Quantitative Experiments				Comparative Experiments							
		Translation		Rotation		Translation				Rotation			
		Chicken	Pork	Chicken	Pork	I	II	III	IV	I	II	III	IV
IoU (%)	min.	69.07	73.81	71.78	73.47	76.17	52.52	50.13	32.69	72.44	61.35	50.71	46.85
	avg.	85.46	79.02	83.81	83.49	81.03	67.31	69.40	52.53	83.66	77.70	68.98	60.57
	max.	94.70	90.02	93.29	92.47	85.25	84.26	88.90	73.62	90.38	83.71	81.19	74.80
Centroid Error (mm)	min.	1.50	1.02	0.60	0.70	0.70	5.20	4.40	8.50	0.70	1.20	0.90	1.30
	avg.	5.49	6.13	4.11	5.08	5.59	12.84	11.80	21.25	4.00	4.47	7.91	11.47
	max.	13.50	10.04	11.80	9.90	9.80	20.40	20.90	32.30	7.80	10.20	18.90	29.20
Orientation Deviation (°)	min.	0.03	0.97	0.35	0.47	1.29	2.34	2.11	3.61	0.17	9.09	7.14	15.93
	avg.	6.39	3.52	7.42	3.98	7.54	8.68	6.42	11.27	5.13	13.83	18.41	30.66
	max.	23.72	8.26	21.84	8.80	12.12	12.68	13.90	30.28	10.95	24.12	27.23	51.02

nearly zero centroid errors and orientation deviations, as the contact did not significantly impact the object’s movement. Therefore, these zero results were excluded from the table.

FIGURE 11. The comparison of different heuristic approaches with translation and rotation experiments. Red: Proposed method, Yellow: Object’s Subcentroids, Purple: Trisecting Object’s Baseline, Blue: Single-point Pushing.

Figure 12 shows that most of the object body near the significant subcentroid fits in the estimated area. However, the other end of the object suffered greater deformation, causing evaluation loss. In addition, the predicted and actual rigid-like contours intersect around selected MPs. This opens the idea of undoing the deformation by extending trajectories of EEs by following points in C_{rigid}^{est} and $C_{projection}^{est}$

(a) Translation: 59mm **(b) Rotation: 94°**
IoU ratio: 88.33% **IoU ratio: 76.95%**

FIGURE 12. The experiments on chicken breast #3. Green & white contours indicate $C_{projection}$ & $C_{desired}$. Red & blue contours indicate C_{rigid} of object & prediction. Teal and orange vectors show the trajectory of P_{left} , P_{right} .

after the sliding motions. Overall, the results show that the proposed solution satisfied the objective and achieved a good score with evaluation metrics of IoU ratios and centroid errors.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper proposes two vision-based manipulation primitives to rearrange the position and orientation of a 3D-DO having biological tissues on a flat surface using a dual-arm robot with passive end-effectors. The manipulation goal was achieved by finding the MPs and generating motion primitives for TCPs, which include deforming and sliding motions. This approach was tested for different meat products through experiments and evaluated its performance using metrics such as IoU contours ratio

and centroid errors, which yielded satisfactory numerical results. In addition, it was compared with other heuristics used on rigid objects and showed a better performance evaluation.

Limitations. The proposed heuristic approach has been numerically validated for certain meat products but relies on assumptions of predominant convexity and uniform density for geometric data utilisation. Force/tactile sensing and learning-based approaches were not considered, leaving both areas for future exploration. Furthermore, the approach can be expanded to incorporate advanced manipulation techniques that have been studied for rigid objects, such as shape control or blending translation and rotation motion primitives.

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